

SEMANTICS OF THE SPEECH VERBS *SPEAK, TALK* IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *Semantics the branch of linguistics and logic concerned with meaning. The two main areas are logical semantics, concerned with matters such as sense and reference and presupposition and implication, and lexical semantics, concerned with the analysis of word meanings and relations between them. Semantics is the study of the meaning of words and sentences. It uses the relations of linguistic forms to non-linguistic concepts and mental representations to explain how sentences are understood by native speakers. This article devoted to the classification of the speech verbs and semantic characteristics of the verbs speak, talk in the English language.*

Key words: *speak, talk, transfer of information, expression, expression of thought, give out a secret; to order, to give commands, judge, evaluate something, distinguish, distinguish, to testify, to affect something.*

INTRODUCTION

The verb *speak* has one or more subject-oriented features: animation, activity, volitiveness and controllability. The subject with the verb *speak* can be characterized as active, that is, being a source of its own energy for the implementation of certain actions; volitional, that is, consciously initiating these actions; and also as controlling the execution of certain events.

METHODS

The author of the explanatory dictionary of verbs L.G. Babenko identifies such classes within the framework of LSG verbs of speech:

- verbs of characterized speech activity;
- verbs of the speech message;
- verbs of speech communication;
- verbs of conversion;
- verbs of speech influence.

Vasiliev L.M. identifies two main oppositions, which include verbs of speech.

A.A. Zaliznyak not only identifies separate classes of verbs, the interpretation of which includes the verb "TO SPEAK", but also gives words with which these verbs can be combined.

RESULTS AND ANALYSES

According to the definition of this verb, rendering to explanatory dictionaries, the following groups of meanings are distinguished:

- 1) *to talk about something;*
- 2) *to say something;*
- 3) *to describe;*
- 4) *to speak in any language;*
- 5) *to speak, to make a speech;*
- 6) *to assert something.*

The selection of the near, far and extreme peripheries is carried out by us through the construction of the lexical and phraseological field of the keyword *speak*. Thus, synonymous words and phrases are presented in six synonymous series, each of which carries its own differential feature. The total number of synonyms of the verb *speak* is 103 linguistic units.

The analysis of the semantics of the core of the nominative field, which includes the direct nomination of the concept under study, namely the verb *to speak*, allowed us to identify the following semantic components: *to speak orally, to use any language, for example:*

Karim speaks English. First think then speak.

The analysis of the semantics of the core of the nominative field, which includes the direct nomination of the concept under study, namely the verb *speak*, allowed us to identify the following semantic components: *to master oral speech, to use any language, for example:*

The drummer usually allowed his ardent good-nature to get the better of his speech. (T.Dreiser, Sister Carrie, 111).

In the zone of the near periphery, the following semantic components can be distinguished: words and phrases: *converse, talk, discuss, chat, chitchat, confabulate, confab, coze, pass the time of day, tell, yap, rap, chin, chew the rag, shoot the breeze, bull* are united by the meaning "to have a friendly conversation, to chat", the *communicate language units*, united by the meaning of "having a friendly conversation, chatting", *language units communicate, inform, advise, apprise, notify, give notice to, give word to, mention to, point out, bring to attention, let know, have*

one to know, give one to understand, enlighten, clue in, open eyes transmit the value "inform, inform, highlight the main thing":

Her picture was in the "World" once or twice, and an old "Herald" he found in a chair informed him that she had recently appeared with some others at a benefit for something or other. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 277).

DISCUSSION

Verbs such as convey, relate, put across, get across are characterized by the general meaning "to develop a thought, to spread". The words and phrases disclose, reveal, divulge, bring out, make known, lay open carry the general meaning of "to expose, to reveal a secret". In the zone of the far periphery, which includes 19 constituents, the following semantic components can be distinguished: the verbs say, utter, express, breathe, whisper, give or let out, come out with, blurt out are united by the meaning of "pronounce, insert, speak in a whisper":

He cursed the luck that could keep him smiling, bowing, shamming, when he wanted to tell her that he loved her, when he wanted to whisper to her alone. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 116).

The words and phrases speak up, speak out, open one's mouth, pipe up, bark convey the general meaning of "keep (conduct) speech":

"Would you mind coming to the box-office a few moments before you dress?" observed the manager, in addition. "There's a little matter I want to speak to you about."

"Certainly," replied Carrie. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 270).

The verbs articulate, enunciate, enounce, pronounce, voice, vocalize are characterized by the meaning "to pronounce clearly, to say". In the zone of the extreme periphery, the following differential signs can be distinguished: the words and phrases discourse, make a speech, give a talk, deliver an address, address, soapbox, platform convey the meaning "to speak, broadcast, address someone". The verbs declare, hold forth, orate, lecture, sermonize, preach, pontificate are united by the meaning "to preach, to teach, to rant".

The verbs harangue, rant, out-herod Herod, spout, spiel, spruik are characterized by the general meaning "to speak loudly and angrily, to criticize".

The words and phrases signify, import, point to, give a token or sign of, betoken, bespeak, show, demonstrate, display, evince, exhibit, manifest, betray, give away carry the general meaning of "to testify, to point to something". The verbs indicate, imply, intimate, mean, denote, connote, suggest, purport are combined with the meaning "to hint at something, to suggest".

The analysis of the semantics of phraseological units included in the nominative field with the keyword *speak* also allows us to identify a number of signs characterizing the way of expressing the concept under study in the language, namely: *pass the time of day – to chat, to pass the time; chew the rag – to chat, scratch your tongue, gossip; shoot the breeze – to talk a lot, spend time talking; open eyes – open your eyes to something.*

They were talking at the breakfast table, a morning or two later, when she brought up the dramatic subject by saying that she saw that Sarah Bernhardt was coming to this country. Hurstwood had seen it, too. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 222). Several young merrymakers were chattering at the bar before making a belated visit to the theatre. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 156).

In accordance with the analysis of the semantic components included in the nominative field with the keyword representative of *speak*, we can make the following cognitive interpretation of them. Thus, the cognitive feature "the ability to use language" is allocated in the core. The zone of the near periphery can be characterized by cognitive signs "friendly conversation", "informing", "disclosure of a secret". The far periphery is interpreted as "utterance of thoughts", "oratory".

And finally, in the zone of the extreme periphery, it is interpreted as "advice" and "perseverance".

The analysis of explanatory dictionaries allows us to distinguish the following groups of meanings of the verb *talk*:

1) *to talk to someone; "Well," he said, "I want to talk to you. You're not going anywhere in particular, are you?" (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 156).*

2) *to discuss something important, serious; It was customary for them to discuss the regular summer outing at this season of the year. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 117)*

3) *to pronounce words in any language; Pronounce words correctly in English.*

4) *to gossip; She gave vent to her opinions in the kitchen where the cook was. As a result, a hum of gossip was set going which moved about the house in that secret manner common to gossip. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 81).*

5) *to present any information (in some cases forcibly). Unquestionably, it was because at that time he had represented something which she did not have; but this she did not understand. Success had given her the momentary feeling that she was now blessed with much of which he would approve. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 291).*

The study of the semantics of the core of the nominative field, which includes the direct nomination of the concept under study, namely the verb *talk*, allowed us to identify the following semantic components: *talk, discuss, chat*:

“Well,” he said, “I want to talk to you. You’re not going anywhere in particular, are you?”

“Not just now,” said Carrie. (T. Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 37).

When Carrie had returned home, flushed with her first success and ready, for all her weariness, to discuss the now interesting events which led up to her achievement, the former had merely smiled approvingly and inquired whether she would have to spend any of it for car fare (T. Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 19).

If he ever approached intoxication—or rather that ruddy warmth and comfortableness which precedes the more sloven state—it was when individuals such as these were gathered about him, when he was one of a circle of chatting celebrities. (T. Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 156).

Language units that are part of the near periphery have the following semantic components: the words and phrases *communicate, converse, exchange ideas, rap or rap with, speak with or to, have a talk or little talk with, consult, conference, check with, parley, palaver, discuss, talk over, consider* are united by the common meaning *"to communicate, exchange opinions, experience (sometimes to to make a decision)"*, *"to chat about trifles, about something not important"*, language units *gossip, buzz, tell secrets or confidences, blab, circulate or spread rumors, dish the dirt, talk behind back* contains the semantic component *"gossip (often with a negative meaning)"*:

Not long after she arrived Mrs. Hale established social relations with her, and together they went about. For a long time this was her only companionship, and the gossip of the manager’s wife formed the medium through which she saw the world. (T. Dreiser, Sister Carrier, 64).

Verbs such as *whisper, breathe* are characterized by the meaning *"to speak softly, to whisper"*:

“Carrie,” he half whispered, “can I have a few words with you?” (T. Dreiser, Sister Carrier, 290).

The verbs *chatter, jabber, prattle, cackle, gibber, gibber-jabber* are united by the meaning *"excited and talk fast, spar"*.

The verbs *babble, prate, tattle, twaddle, twattle* are characterized by a common semantic component *"babble, babble"*. The language units *tongue twister, babble, chatter, bullshit* contain the meaning *"to talk nonsense, to grind nonsense"*.

The verbs *mumble, mumble, stutter, stutter, sputter, spit out* are defined by the common sema *"mumble, sigh through your teeth, stutter with anger"*:

Then the sheer loneliness of his situation rushed upon him in full.

“Left me!” he muttered, and repeated, “left me!” (T. Dreiser. Sister Carrier. 265)

The constituents *chat, chitchat, chitter-chatter, chaffer, bandy words, chin, confabulate, confab, coze, pass the time of day* are united by the meaning "chat, spend time talking". The words and phrases *talk idly, visit, shoot the breeze, chew the fat or rag, jaw, gas, gab, bull or shoot the bull* contain the semantic sign "to talk for a very long time".

The verbs *palaver, clack, clatter, yap, yak, yackety-yak, schmooze* are characterized by the seme "to talk nonsense, nonsense".

The language units *rattle, rattle on, go on, bend ear off, run off or on at the mouth, have diarrhea of the mouth* have a common meaning of "talking for a long time and without stopping, chattering". The words and phrases *be loquacious, ramble (on), maunder, digress, go off on a tangent* contain this "to tire with your speech, story":

To one not inclined to drink, and gifted with a more serious turn of mind, such a bubbling, chattering, glittering chamber must ever seem an anomaly, a strange commentary on nature and life. (T.Dreiser. Sister Carrier, 30).

In the far periphery, during the semantic description of the linguistic units included in this zone, the following semantic components are distinguished: words and phrases *to open the mouth, speak, articulate, pronounce, express, pronounce, voice, give voice or mouth, make sounds, put into words* are united by the meaning of "pronounce sounds, syllables, words":

In the far periphery, during the semantic description of the language units included in this zone, the following semantic components are distinguished: words and phrases *to open the mouth, speak, articulate, pronounce, express, pronounce, voice, give voice or mouth, make sounds, put into words* are united by the meaning of "pronounce sounds, syllables, words".

Those who had been waiting before him, but farther away, now drew near, and by a certain stolidity of demeanour, no words being spoken, indicated that they were first (T.Dreiser, Sister Carrier, 295).

The language units *express, express their opinion, speak out, get out, express their opinion, invest their two cents, express their opinion, say what's on your mind* contain the semantic component "explain, speak out".

The verbs of *air, ventilation, ventilation* are characterized by a common seme "to publicly, openly reason, convey your thoughts, ideas":

Hopelessly he turned back into Broadway again and slopped onward and away, begging, crying, losing track of his thoughts, one after another, as a mind decayed and disjointed is wont to do (T.Dreiser, Sister Carrier, 299).

The constituents *discourse, make a speech, give a talk, deliver an address, address, soapbox, platform* are defined by the meaning "to state a firm belief, to address someone".

The verbs *declare, orate, lecture, sermonize, preach, pontificate* and the phrasal verb *hold forth* are united by the meaning "to preach, to prove your case."

She realized that hers was not to be a round of pleasure, and yet there was something promising in all the material prospect he set forth(T.Dreiser, *Sister Carrier*, 6).

The verbs *harangue, rant, out-herod Herod* are characterized by a common semantic component "to criticize, express your dissatisfaction", while the verbs *rhapsodize, gush, spout* contain the meaning "to speak eloquently, with enthusiasm".

The zone of the extreme periphery, which includes 32 constituents, is defined by the following meanings: verbs and verb combinations *to divulge, disclose, make public, give out, proceed from the fact that to blurt out, let slip or fall, release, spill, put one foot in your mouth* are united by the meaning "to reveal a secret; insert a word (without thinking), to get into a conversation", the phraseological unit *put one foot in your mouth* conveys the meaning "to offend someone, to harm by saying something superfluous".

The verbs *express, pronounce, say, declare, declare, proclaim* are characterized by the phrase "express an opinion, declare":

Polished brass or nickel signs at the square stone entrances announced the firm and the nature of the business in rather neat and reserved terms (T.Dreiser, *Sister Carrier*, 12)

The verbs *recount, relate, convey, put or get across* contain the semantic component "to share experiences, memories" and "to convey your thoughts to others, to spread", for example:

On the ceilings were coloured traceries with more gilt, leading to a centre where spread a cluster of lights—incandescent globes mingled with glittering prisms and stucco tendrils of gilt(T.Dreiser, *Sister Carrier*, 193).

The language units *tell, inform, advise, notify, give word to, let know, bring to attention, point out, enlighten, clue in, tip off, give one to understand* are defined by the meaning "inform, advise, warn".

On Wednesday he received another polite note from McGregor, James and Hay. It read:

"Dear Sir: We beg to inform you that we are instructed to wait until to-morrow (Thursday) at one o'clock, before filing suit against you, on behalf of Mrs. Julia Hurstwood, for divorce and alimony(T.Dreiser, *Sister Carrier*, 146).

So, in the core, we distinguish the cognitive sign of *"having a conversation"*.

"You will be in Chicago some little time, won't you?" he observed at one turn of the now easy conversation(T.Dreiser, Sister Carrier, 6).

The zone of the near periphery can be interpreted as *"spending time"*, *"manner of conversation"* and *"way of expressing thoughts"*.

In the zone of the far periphery, the cognitive signs *"the ability to speak"* and *"persuasion"* are distinguished.

He tried the art of persuasion with all his powers aroused(T.Dreiser, Sister Carrier,163).

The extreme periphery has cognitive signs of *"speaking as harming"* and *"caring"*.

CONCLUSION

This study allows to draw the following conclusions: syntax by itself is not similar social factor; the role similar social criteria for the allocation of values of speech verbs plays a syntactic structure, combined with the force index syntax indicators.

Thus, we can say that speech verbs belong to the group of verbs in which the relationship between the functional purpose of verbs, their lexical expression and syntactic constructions is most clearly used.

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